

e-ISSN: 3048-9709

Volume 08 Issue 01 Jan-
Apr 2026

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Submission Date: Dec 19,
2025

Copyright Received Date:
Dec 23, 2025

Automatic On/Off Temperature Sensor Fan

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ABSTRACT

Controlled Automatic temperature- fan system. The primary objective is to create a low-cost, reliable circuit that automatically activates a cooling fan when the ambient temperature rises above a predetermined threshold and deactivates it once the temperature drops. This is achieved without using microcontroller or any programming. The core system is an NTC thermistor acting as the temperature sensor, which triggers a 5V relay module to switch a DC fan motor on or off. The project demonstrates a fundamental application of analog electronics for automated environmental control, offering simple and effective for cooling small spaces and electronic components.

Keywords:- *Automatic temperature control, NTC thermistor, 5V relay module, DC fan, analog electronics, thermal sensing, cooling system, temperature- activated circuit, automation*

INTRODUCTION

Regulation of Temperature is essential in many electrical and environmental applications, especially where continuous heat buildup can affect system performance. Conventional systems operation, which may or component life. Often rely on manual cause unnecessary power consumption or delayed response to rising temperatures.

To overcome these limitations, automatic temperature-controlled systems provide an efficient and responsive alternative. The Automatic On–Off Temperature Sensor Fan is a simple, low-cost solution that uses analog electronic components to achieve automatic cooling control. The circuit is built around an NTC thermistor, whose resistance varies with temperature, enabling it to sense even small changes in ambient conditions.

This change in resistance is used to trigger a 5V relay module, which switches a DC fan on when temperature rises a preset threshold and turns it off as the temperature decreases. Unlike microcontroller-based systems, working of this system does not require programming, making it for beginners and useful for demonstrating the fundamental principles of sensors, switching circuits, and thermal control.

The design is compact, reliable, and energy-efficient, making it ideal for small electronic setups, mini enclosures, and

basic cooling applications. This paper focused on the practical use of analog electronics in real- world automation and environmental management.

METHODOLOGY AND WORKING PRINCIPLE

The paper`s methodology centers on thermistor of NTC type that continuously monitors the ambient temperature.

This sensor is combined with voltage divider circuit, where its resistance decreases when temperature rises, causing a corresponding change in the circuit's voltage output.

When the temperature surpasses a predetermined threshold, this voltage change is significant enough to trigger a control element, such as a transistor or an operational amplifier comparator. This amplified signal then energizes a 5V relay module, which functions as an electronic switch. The activation of the relay completes the circuit between a 9V battery and a DC motor fan, causing the fan to turn on and cool the area. Conversely, once the temperature drops below the set threshold, the thermistor's resistance increases, reversing the voltage signal, which deactivates the relay.

This action cuts off the power supply to the fan, causing it to stop automatically, thus completing the automated control cycle.

Fig.1:-Block Diagram

Working Principle: The working principle of an automatic temperature-controlled fan using analog electronics begins with a thermistor sensor, which is a type of resistor whose resistance changes as temperature shifts. At lower or room temperatures, the thermistor's high

resistance keeps the circuit's output voltage below the threshold required to activate the relay coil, ensuring the relay remains in its default state and fan is off. As the environment heats up, thermistor's resistance drops, which raises the voltage across the control circuit.

Fig.2:- Circuit diagram

When this voltage crosses the preset trigger level, it energizes a transistor that switches on the relay module. The relay then acts as an electrical switch, closing its contacts to allow the 9V battery to power the DC fan motor. The fan begins

to run, providing cooling until the temperature drops below the set point. Once the temperature falls sufficiently, the voltage through the thermistor returns below the threshold, turning off the relay and stopping the fan.

RESULT

When temperature increases Thermistor resistance decreases. Thermistor is connected with a fixed resistor (10kΩ). Together they form a voltage divider. The output voltage is: $V(\text{out}) = V_{cc} \times [R(\text{NTC})/R(\text{NTC})+10k]$ Where: $V_{cc} = 3.7V$ (battery to sensor) $R(\text{NTC}) =$ thermistor resistance at that temperature

The relay gets ON when: $V(\text{out}) = 2.2V$ (approx.). This is the "trigger point." Putting V_{cc} and $V(\text{out})$ in above equation,

$$[2.2/3.7] = [R(\text{NTC})/\{R(\text{NTC})+10K\}]$$

$$0.59 = [R(\text{NTC})/\{R(\text{NTC})+10K\}] \quad 0.59R(\text{NTC})+5900=R(\text{NTC}) \quad 0.41R(\text{NTC})=5900 \quad R(\text{NTC})=[5900/0.41]=14.4k\Omega.$$

Fig.3:-experimental setup

Fig.4:-result of the circuit

When the thermistor reaches 14.4kΩ, the relay turns ON, and the fan starts rotating. At 25°C, thermistor = 10kΩ At higher temperature, resistance becomes less than 10kΩ, At lower temperature, resistance becomes more than 10kΩ. Since 14.4kΩ is higher than 10kΩ, it means the temperature is BELOW

25°C. Temperature instantly rises above 40°C. Resistance drops very fast (below 5kΩ).

This makes the relay switch ON immediately → fan starts rotating. Fan turns ON when thermistor reaches ≈ 14.4kΩ. In real testing, this happens at around 40–70°C.

CONCLUSION

The Automatic On–Off Temperature Sensor Fan project successfully demonstrates how a simple and cost-effective analog circuit can be used to achieve automatic temperature control without the need for microcontrollers or programming. By utilizing an NTC thermistor as the temperature-sensing element and a 5V relay module for switching, the system effectively activates a DC fan when the ambient temperature rises and turns it off once the temperature returns to normal.

This paper emphasizes practical use of basic electronic components in real-world thermal management and offers a reliable solution for maintaining optimal temperature in small enclosures or electronic devices.

Its ease of construction, low power consumption, and consistent performance make it a suitable choice for beginners and educational demonstrations. Overall, the project fulfills its objective of providing an efficient, automatic cooling mechanism using simple analog electronics.

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